

CARBON/PP COMPOSITES AND CARBON/SELF-REINFORCED PP COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Carbon/PP and carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites have been produced by film-stacking. Tensile tests in carbon/PP composites show that the E-modulus is 15% lower than expected. Compared to carbon/PP materials, hybrid composites show an increase of 6-20% in ultimate strain and 10-15% in strength, while the E-modulus is kept as predicted.

Keywords: Carbon reinforced thermoplastics, Self-reinforced polypropylene, hybrid composite, mechanical testing

INTRODUCTION

Carbon reinforced thermoplastics represent an alternative to obtain light materials with high specific mechanical properties, avoiding intrinsic drawbacks of reinforced thermosets like long curing times and hazardous chemical substances. Furthermore, thermoplastic composites can also be re-melted, post-processed and recycled. In addition, due to its lightness, low-cost, and low Life Cycle Analysis impact, polypropylene is increasingly used as matrix thermoplastic composites.

However, the main shortcoming of carbon composites is their brittleness and their bad impact performance, which might hopefully be overcome by hybridisation with self-reinforced polypropylene. Self-reinforced PP (produced by Propex under the tradename CURV[®]) is chemically identical to PP, so it is as light and recyclable as the normal polymer. However, it has been found to be 3 to 5 times stiffer than polypropylene, as well as extremely tough and impact resistant [1]. Furthermore, self-reinforced PP, as well as CURV[®], has been shown to undergo shrinkage while heating up to processing temperatures [2]. This effect may lead to dimensional problems when only-CURV[®] products are made, but on the other hand, it can also be exploited to induce compressive stresses when laminating together with another material.

From another point of view, hybrid composites are defined as composites made out of two sorts of fibres, for instance stiff and brittle fibres combined with less stiff but tough fibres, embedded in the same matrix. Because of several mechanisms like thermal residual stresses, or energetic effects due to arresting of cracks initiated in the stiff fibre layer or area by the tough fibres; such hybridization may lead to a synergetic effect in mechanical performance, meaning an increase in the ultimate strain compared with the ultimate strain of the brittle fibre composite, while achieving a higher stiffness. This has

been widely investigated both experimentally [3], [4], [5], [6] and theoretically [7], [8], [9], [10].

Thus, if CURV[®] layers are stacked together with carbon/PP layers (interply hybrid), compressive stresses due to a controlled shrinkage of CURV[®], may be induced in carbon fibres, increasing this way their apparent strength and ultimate failure strain in the composite. A further improvement could be realized when layers of highly-oriented PP tapes and layers of carbon fibres are embedded in the same low-oriented PP matrix, resulting in an intraply hybrid composite.

As it has been mentioned before, there already exists wide research work dealing with the hybrid synergetic effect on mechanical properties of hybrid composites, but the challenge lays on the fact that no studies on the hybridisation of self-reinforced polymers have been yet published.

The present study aims first to study the processability and mechanical performance of carbon/PP single composites, and to further hybridise them with self-reinforced PP. Then, the challenge is to obtain carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites, which will benefit from the inherent toughness of CURV[®], from the hybrid synergetic effect in ultimate strain, and from induced compressive stresses in carbon fibres due to a controlled shrinkage of CURV[®] during the manufacturing process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Maleic anhydride modified polypropylene films from Amcor have been used for impregnating carbon weaves. The thickness of these films is 100 microns, the density is 0,9 g/cm³, the melt flow index is 5,2 g/10min, and standard DSC tests have shown that the melting point is 162,5°C.

Twill 2/2 carbon fabrics from Hexcel (Hexcel G0986 D1200) with nominal weight of 285 g/m², and nominal construction of 3,5 picks/cm and 3,5 counts/cm have been used as reinforcement material. Yarns from Toho-Tenax (Tenax HTA 5131 6K) were used to weave the previously mentioned carbon fabrics. 6000 filaments with 6 microns diameter were used to form the yarns, leading to a linear density of 400 tex. The mechanical properties of these fibres are the following: tensile strength of 3950 MPa, tensile modulus of 238 GPa, and elongation at break of 1,7%.

Self-reinforced PP tapes from Propex (standard CURV[®] material) are woven into fabrics and then consolidated into sheets of 150 and 300 microns thickness. Because of the fact that self-reinforced PP is chemically identical to normal PP, its density is only 0,92 g/cm³, while the mechanical properties of the CURV[®] woven fabric sheets rise up to the following values: tensile modulus of 3 GPa, tensile strength of 160 MPa and elongation at break of 16%.

Processing methods

Composite plates have been made by hot-press in a Pinnette press Zenith 2, which can apply forces up to 40 Ton and temperatures up to 500°C. Film-stacking technology has been used to impregnate carbon fabrics with polypropylene films. Afterwards, hot-pressure compactation has been applied to laminate various monolayers of PP impregnated carbon fabrics and to consolidate hybrid composites with alternating layers

of self-reinforced PP and PP impregnated carbon fabrics. 300 mm x 300 mm samples, processed at different conditions, have been produced and tested in order to study the dependence of their mechanical properties on processing parameters such as temperature, pressure and processing time.

Carbon/Self-Reinforced PP hybrid composites have been made stacking together CURV[®] layers with carbon fabrics impregnated beforehand at optimal conditions. The processing temperature is always kept between 165 and 175°C in order to avoid degradation of the highly-oriented polypropylene tapes in the CURV[®] sheets. This way, hybrid composite plates with different interply stacking sequences have been made in order to determine their mechanical properties and to analyse the hybrid effect.

Quality assessment and mechanical testing methods

First of all, the density of the composite (ρ_C) is calculated using Equation 1. For that purpose, the average thickness of the composite plate (h_C) is measured with the precision down to 10 microns, and the mass of the composite plate (M_C) is measured with a microbalance down to 0,1 g. Then, the fibre volume fraction can be easily calculated with Equation 2, where $A_f=285$ g/m² is the areal weight of the carbon fabric, A is the area of carbon fabric, N_L is the number of layers and ρ_f is the density of carbon fibre, 1,76 g/cm³.

$$\rho_C \left(\frac{g}{cm^3} \right) = \frac{M_C (g)}{10^4 A (m^2) \cdot 0,1 h_C (mm)} \quad (1)$$

$$V_f = \frac{A_f \times A \times N_L \rho_C}{M_C \rho_f} \quad (2)$$

$$V_f = \frac{A \times A_f / \rho_f}{A \times A_f / \rho_f + (1 - A \times A_f) / \rho_m + Vol_Voids} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{Voids} = \frac{Vol_Voids}{M_f / \rho_f + M_m / \rho_m + Vol_Voids} \quad (4)$$

In order to calculate the void content of the material, the volume occupied by void inside the composite plate (Vol_Voids) can be derived from Equation 3, where ρ_M is the density of the matrix ($\rho_M = \rho_{PP} = 0,9$ g/cm³). Finally, the volume fraction of void is easily calculated by means of Equation 4. All the voids are concentrated in the fibre region (inside the yarns), so the average non-impregnated cross-sectional area of the yarns can be obtained dividing the void volume fraction by the fibre volume fraction. In order to qualitatively analyse the quality of the impregnation, cross-sectional optical microscopical characterization has been also carried out.

Tensile tests in the 0° degree direction on 250 mm x 25 mm specimens have been carried out using an INSTRON 4467 tensile testing machine with a load cell of 30 kN

and a cross-head speed of 2mm/min. An extensometer has been used to measure the real strain during the tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carbon/polypropylene composites

Qualitative analysis of cross-sections allows distinguishing whether a sample is bad impregnated or not, and better impregnation is seen in samples where the calculated void content and non impregnated area are lower; see Fig 1.

Fig 1. Cross-sectional optical micrographs of carbon/PP samples. Left side: Big non-impregnated area. Right side: Small non-impregnated area.

On the other hand, quantitative analysis is also done using eq. 4, and numerical values can be obtained. The calculated void contents for different processing conditions are shown in Table 1. It can be seen that the stronger the processing conditions are (higher temperature, higher pressure, and longer time), the higher the fibre volume fraction is, and the lower the void content and non-impregnation area are.

Table 1. Fibre volume fraction and void content of carbon/PP composites

Processing Paramters				Measured	Calculated			
Code	Temp. (C)	Pres. (bar)	Time (min)	t (mm)	ρ_c (g/cm ³)	Vf(%)	Void (%)	Non. I. Area (%)
C_1	180	20	10	1,074	1,210	45,24	8,21	18,15
C_2	200	20	10	1,021	1,229	47,58	8,37	17,59
C_3	220	20	10	0,916	1,324	53,02	2,95	5,57
C_4	220	40	10	0,860	1,371	56,51	1,12	1,98
C_5	220	20	30	0,964	1,269	50,39	6,55	13,01
C_6	220	20	50	0,889	1,344	54,65	3,04	5,57
C_7	220	30	30	0,842	1,360	57,68	3,49	6,06
C_8	220	30	50	0,815	1,388	59,62	2,28	3,83

At temperatures above 220°C, some of the curing agents which are present in the carbon fibre sizings would start degrading, so the maximum processing temperature for the system carbon/PP is 220°C. At pressures above 30 bars, carbon yarns become damaged during the processing, so the maximum allowed pressure is about 30 bars. In addition, long processing times help the impregnation and diminish the influence of the applied pressure.

Tensile tests have shown first of all that the failure modes are consistent with microscopical analysis (impregnation quality). Good impregnated samples (Fig. 3: right side) present higher E-modulus, break at higher stresses and strains, in a brittle way, perpendicularly to the loading direction; while bad impregnated samples (Fig. 3: left side), have lower E-modulus, break in different directions at lower stresses and strains.

Fig. 3. Modes of failure of carbon/PP composites after tensile testing in 0 degree direction. Left side: bad impregnated sample. Right side: good impregnated sample.

Second, non-linear stress-strain behaviour has been observed in all the carbon/PP tested specimens. As it is shown in the Fig. 4, (E modulus Vs Strain), the E modulus of the carbon/PP composites increases 20-30% during the loading state. The same behaviour (up to 20%) has been already observed on single carbon fibres [11]. The other 10% may be explained because of the initial crimp (fibres are not completely straightened) of the carbon fabric and the inherent weakness of the polypropylene matrix, which allows de-crimping and fibre straightening at strains higher then 0.5%.

Fig. 4. Non-linear stress-strain behaviour of carbon/PP composites

The mechanical properties of the studied carbon/PP composites are summarized in Table 2. It can be observed that the higher the fibre volume fraction is (and the lower the void content), the better the mechanical performance of the composite is. Thus, the best possible processing conditions for film-stacking of polypropylene with carbon fabrics are 220°C, 20-30 bars and 50 min of hot-pressing. The obtained properties are: E modulus of 50 GPa, strength of 644 MPa and elongation at break of 1,19%.

Table 2. Mechanical properties of carbon/PP composites

Code	Vf(%)	Void (%)	E Modulus (GPa)		Strength (MPa)		Ult. Strain (%)	
			Average	Scatter	Average	Scatter	Average	Scatter
C_1	45,24	8,21	47,81	11,44 %	452	4,09 %	0,97	5,63 %
C_2	47,58	8,37	46,19	3,33 %	449	5,42 %	0,93	6,34 %
C_3	53,02	2,95	54,12	4,98 %	524	4,40 %	0,92	3,72 %
C_4	56,51	1,12	50,21	13,04 %	534	12,52 %	0,97	5,53 %
C_5	50,39	6,55	47,81	11,44 %	561	8,04 %	1,12	13,77 %
C_6	54,65	3,04	50,65	9,89 %	644	3,26 %	1,19	5,02 %
C_7	57,68	3,49	47,53	15,12 %	608	5,62 %	1,11	10,01 %
C_8	59,62	2,28	45,89	12,68 %	672	8,67 %	1,28	11,00 %

In order to know if these results fit with expectations, various predictions have been made. The experimental data from a carbon/PP composite pressed at optimal conditions (220C, 20 bars and 50 min) together with 3 different predictions is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig.6 Carbon/PP composites. Comparison between experimental data and predictions.

The first prediction considers the twill weave as a 0/90 laminate, for which a simple, isostrain-based rule-of-mixture is used: $E_{0/90} = \frac{1}{2} (E_0 + E_{90})$. Hence, for a given fibre volume fraction and full impregnation, the E-modulus of a PP impregnated twill 2/2 carbon weave should be $E_f \cdot V_f / 2$ GPa. As the transversal modulus of carbon yarns is much lower than the longitudinal, the contribution of the fibres in 90 degree direction can be neglected.

In addition, the waviness of a twill 2/2 weave is relatively small so the crimp effect can also be neglected. Thus, the only effect which can lower the E-modulus from such an ideal value is the presence of voids and non-impregnated areas.

As the assumption is that the entire load is carried by the fibres and that non-impregnated fibres do not contribute to the stiffness of the material, the expected E modulus should be expressed as in the equation 6.

$$E_1 = E_{f,t} \times \left(\frac{V_f}{2} \right) \times (1 - NonIArea) \quad (6)$$

where *NonIArea* is the averaged relative area of non-impregnate zones on the cross-section. A further improvement of the modulus predictions can be achieved by taking into account the increase of the tangent modulus as function of the applied strain. The tangent E modulus of the carbon fibres themselves, according to our experimental data and results of other investigations [11] raises up about 20% during the loading state ($E_{\text{fibre,tangent,final}} = 1,2 * E_{\text{fibre,tangent,initial}}$).

The second prediction has been carried out using Wisetex and Texcomp software [12]. For this calculation the fibre volume fraction has been considered as the volume fraction of impregnated fibres $V_{f_Imp} = V_f * (1 - NonIArea)$. In this case, contribution of fibres in 90 degree direction is taken into account, so is the effects of the crimp, which is calculated to be of 0,1%.

The third prediction represents the ideal case if full impregnation was achieved.

If experimental curves are compared with the predictions, E modulus and strength are 15% lower than expected. The reason may be that the adhesion between carbon fibres and polypropylene is not good enough to correctly transfer the load. In this case, carbon fibres would not contribute 100% to the stiffness of the carbon/PP composite.

Carbon/Self-reinforced polypropylene composites

Several carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites with different CURV[®] to carbon/PP ratios have been produced and tested. The calculated carbon fibre volume fraction and the void content for different hybrid composites are shown on Table 3. It can be seen that the impregnation is worse for hybrid composites. That is explained because in carbon/PP composites, nesting between layers allows better impregnation, while in hybrid composites there is no possibility that such effect arises. The difference in impregnation between carbon/PP and carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites can be appreciated in Fig. 7.

Table 3. Fibre volume fraction and void content of carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites for different processing parameters.

Code	Hybrid stacking sequence	Measured	Calculated			
		t (mm)	ρ_c (g/cm ³)	Vf(%)	Void (%)	Non. I. Area (%)
C_6	CarbonPP/CarbonPP/CarbonPP	0,889	1,344	54,65	3,04	5,57
H_1	Curv/CarbonPP/Curv	0,955	1,037	16,95	3,11	18,35
H_2	Carbon/PP/Curv/CarbonPP	0,987	1,143	32,82	5,07	15,46
H_3	Curv/CarbonPP/Curv/CarbonPP/Curv	1,139	1,128	28,44	3,50	12,32
H_4	Curv/CarbonPP/Curv	0,924	1,047	17,52	2,61	14,90

The results from tensile testing in carbon/self-reinforced PP composites are summarized on Table 4. The ultimate strain of hybrid composites is shown to be 6-20% higher than

for carbon/PP single composites. This increase, which may be attributed to the hybrid effect, fits with the hybrid effects described by other authors [3], [4], [5], [6].

In order to assess the effect of hybridising carbon/PP composites with self-reinforced PP, not only the ultimate strain should be analysed, but also the stiffness and strength. Experimental curves of a hybrid sample together with 3 predictions are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7. Left side: Good impregnated carbon/PP sample. Right side: Carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composite showing a big non-impregnated area.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites.

Code	Vf(%)	Void (%)	E Modulus (GPa)		Strength (MPa)		Ult. Strain (%)	
			Average	Scatter	Average	Scatter	Average	Scatter
C_6	54,65	3,04	50,65	9,89 %	644	3,26 %	1,19	5,02 %
H_1	16,95	3,11	15,38	11,18 %	219	9,26 %	1,27	12,04 %
H_2	32,82	5,07	26,28	15,74 %	398	4,38 %	1,41	6,24 %
H_3	28,44	3,50	22,75	10,84 %	347	5,94 %	1,31	6,26 %
H_4	17,52	2,61	16,41	9,09 %	263	5,55 %	1,43	7,25 %

Fig.8 Carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites. Comparison between experimental data and predictions. Stress/Strain curve

The first prediction [Equation 7] considers the same assumptions as the first prediction for carbon/PP composites. This time the contribution to the stiffness of CURV[®] layers is included. The second prediction [Equation 8] takes the experimentally obtained E modulus of the carbon/PP composite as reference. Then, corrections are applied to account for the difference in impregnated fibre volume fraction (eq.8), and the CURV[®] contribution to the stiffness is added as well. The third prediction represents the ideal case if full impregnation was achieved.

$$E_{H1} = 238 \times \left(\frac{V_{f-Carbon}}{2} \right) \times (1 - NonIArea) + 2,5 \times V_{f-CURV} \quad (7)$$

$$E_{H2} = E_1 \times \left(\frac{V_{f-Carbon-Hybrid}}{V_{f-Carbon-reference}} \right) \times \left(\frac{1 - NonIArea_{Hybrid}}{1 - NonIArea_{reference}} \right) + 2,5 \times V_{f-CURV} \quad (8)$$

If the experimental results are compared to theoretical models (prediction 1), E modulus is about of 15% lower than the expectations. As the ultimate strain is higher, the resulting strength rises up to predicted values. On the other hand, if the comparison is made with experimental results of carbon/PP composites, taking into account the presence of bigger non-impregnated areas in hybrids, the resulting E modulus is kept as expected. Therefore, as there is an increase in ultimate strain, strength values rise up 10-15% above the predicted level.

CONCLUSIONS

Carbon/PP composites and carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites have been produced by film-stacking technology in order to study their mechanical behaviour and the hybrid synergetic effect in ultimate strain, which come up when stiff and tough fibres are embedded in the same matrix.

Microscopical analysis of cross-sections allows distinguishing whether a sample is bad impregnated or not. The influence of the processing parameters on the quality of the impregnation and the mechanical properties of carbon/PP composites has been studied and best processing parameters for 3-layer carbon/PP single composites have been found out to be 220°C, 20-30 bars and 50 min of hot-pressing. Hybrid composites present worse impregnation because nesting between carbon/PP layers is not possible, because of the presence of the flat CURV layers.

Non-linear stress-strain behaviour has been observed in carbon/PP specimens. The E-modulus is shown to increase up to 30% during the loading state. This effect is coherent with the behaviour of carbon fibres themselves shown by [11] and it is amplified by the stretching of the wavy carbon yarns in the weak polypropylene matrix. The stiffness and strength of carbon/PP composites is about 15% lower than expected. Such lower properties may be caused by worse impregnation than calculated, or because of bad adhesion between carbon fibres and polypropylene.

Carbon/self-reinforced PP hybrid composites show an increase of ultimate strain compared to single carbon/PP specimens of 6-20%. This behaviour may be attributed to the synergetic hybrid effect broadly reported in literature [3], [4], [5], [6]. The E modulus of the hybrid composites is 15% lower than expected when compared to

theoretical predictions. On the other hand, if the comparison is made with the experimental data obtained for carbon/PP samples, no further decrease in modulus is observed for hybrid composites, and strength even raises 10-15% above the predictions.

It can be finally concluded that carbon/PP composites do not behave as expected, but the elaboration of hybrid composites with self-reinforced PP leads to a 6-20% synergetic hybrid effect in the ultimate strain of the material, keeping E-modulus as expected from the rule of mixtures, and rising up the strength above the predictions.

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